

THE EXPRESSION OF THE INTENSITY OF WORDS AT LANGUAGE LEVELS

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Abstract: It is known that the word has several meanings, and some means are used to distinguish them from each other, including strengthening words. When we express our thoughts through words, we need amplifiers and units to make this idea more clear and understandable. When expressing colors (it's not just black, dark black makes it even more clear, very dark black, when expressing the dark red state of red (I'm tired, I miss you so much), the amplifying units clarify our thoughts. In the process of expressing thoughts in Uzbek and English languages. To increase the effectiveness of speech, various methods of amplification are used. This article discusses the amplification of meaning in phonetic, lexical, grammatical means.

Keywords: intensity category, phonetic, syntactic, phraseological intensifiers, word formation, special intensifying words, expressiveness, emotionality

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The issues of the intensity category have been attracting the attention of researchers for a long time. Although different opinions and theories appeared in this regard, after the 60s of the 19th century, attention to scientific research in this field increased. On the issue of intensity, one can list the works of scientists such as G. Kirchner, B. Charleston, S. Greenbaum, D. Boldger, Sh. Bally, A. V. Kunin, V. A. Maltsev, T. A. Tsoi. They approached the study of this issue from different points of view. For example, A.V. Kunin analyzed the phenomenon of intensity in English linguistics from a phraseological point of view, and phraseological units expressing strong emotions in many cases indicate expressive expression of thought.

In the research of E.I. Sheygal, an attempt was made to determine the semantic status of the intensity component. In this research, the intensifier is separated from the lexic level as a separate layer. In the research of I.G. Beruchashvili, attention is paid to the expression of the intensity category by lexical means, in which the intensity category is organized according to the "determiner + defined" type model. A. Abdullayev organized the study of meaning enhancement in Uzbek linguistics at the phonetic and morphological levels. Here, it is noted that the phonetic method can be used to strengthen the meaning of the vowel, lengthening the vowel, and gemination (doubling of the sound), and the morphological method of the suffix -lar.

There are different views and opinions about the concept of "intensity" in linguistics. Most of the philologists consider this concept as a manifestation of the quantity category. They consider intensity as a semantic category, and recognize

that the concept of "quantity" is based on its gradation in meaning. The French scientist Sh.Bally approaches the concept in a broader way and describes intensity as related to categories such as quantity, size, value, power. Based on the opinions of the above scientists, the category of intensity is manifested in the increase in the level of expressiveness. The need to determine the level of expressiveness of the lexeme, in turn, requires the introduction of the concept of "intensity scale". For example: to be in love – to be really and truly in love with somebody, to be terribly in love with somebody, to love somebody madness (death), like. If we consider the phrase "To be in love" as a simple starting point of the level of intensity, we can see that the intensity has increased by introducing intensifiers into the composition of this phrase.

Intensity has a phonetic, morphological, lexical, and syntactic expression system at different levels of the language. In this article, we focus on the expression of intensity at the phonetic, lexical, and morphological levels. In English, phonetic amplification of meaning is expressed by the use of strong pronunciation of vowels or consonants, stretching, segmentation, and various components of intonation. For example: Don't tell him – Do-o-o-o-nt tell him. In this example, it can be seen that by lengthening the vowel "o" a number of "additional" meanings are expressed along with increasing intensity – begging, begging, request. As with vowels, the meaning is strengthened by doubling consonants (gemination). For example: I r-r-r-ruin my character by remaining with a Ladyship so inflamed!

Also, in exclamations, the phonetic method is used to increase the meaning according to the feeling. For example: OH! Ah! Pooh! Dear me! God knows! By means of intonation, speech acquires emotional expressiveness. Tone helps to make speech lively and expressive. Intonation in oral speech is expressed by raising or lowering the voice, and in written speech by punctuation, italics. For example: Do you mind opening the window? Shut the door, please! So, intensity is phonetically expressed through means such as lengthening of vowels and consonants, strong pronunciation, intonation and its components, using pauses and strokes.

A morphological method of meaning amplification is meaning amplification using a morpheme. Intensity mainly depends on signs of predication and movement, the nature of the movement and the mental state of the adjuster, his feelings. Among the word groups, adverbial and verb word groups are the basis for strengthening the meaning. One of the categories of adjectives is to strengthen the meaning of adjectives using adjective degrees. The meaning increases in the comparative and accusative degrees of ordinary quality. For example: strong – stronger – the strongest, beautiful – more beautiful – the most beautiful, good – better – the best. The analysis of the examples shows that the morphological enhancement of the meaning is more developed in noun, adjective, and verb

groups than in other groups of words. As a result of the observations, it became known that the following prefixes are very active in strengthening the meanings of adjectives, nouns, and verbs. Super-, over-, out-, can be shown as the most active prefixes. Meaning amplification at the morphological level can be expressed using prefixes, suffixes, postpositives. In general, the serious organization of strengthening the meaning of word in the morphological method is of great importance in revealing the undiscovered aspects of the semantic structure of word and word form.

It is very important to avoid. At the lexical level, meaning enhancement is expressed by means of adverbs, intensifying adjectives, quantifiers, intensifying phraseological units, a synonymous line of adjectives and verbs, and separate sentences. It can be done using the synonym method of strengthening the meaning of action and situation. For example: **Pour or pour down- to rain very hard. The thunder and lightning stopped but it continued to pour.** At the lexical level, lexemes such as **jolly, pretty, dead, badly** can also be used to express intensity, which in many cases express intensity.

**Super- , hyper- , out- , over- , ultra- , extra- ,
micro- , mini- ,
un- , in- , ir- , dis- , etc.**

The category of intensity is inevitably related to the concepts of quantity, quality and gradients. The assessment of quality by intensity is a quantitative indicator and can be included in the quantitative category of language. It represents a group of words that differ according to the degree of manifestation of the intensity feature. Character intensives change over time: some become irrelevant, semantics, on the contrary, are updated. Due to the loss of some intensive substances, it is constantly replenished due to the formation of new agents with an emotional character and enhancing value. The linguistic phenomenon of intensity makes it necessary to study certain intensifier (intensifier) phrases in speech, their analysis. Intensification has two sides:

- 1) external / surface - fig
- 2) internal / deep - content.

The lexical-semantic group of intensifying meaning includes very wide units: completely, definitely, absolutely, extremely. For example, absolute goodness means the complete absence of evil; absolutely smooth means the complete absence of irregularities. The use of these words often has a subjective-evaluative nature inherent in the meaning of intensity. However, it is very difficult to determine the visible differences in the size of the sign expressed by the phrases extremely strong, completely strong absolutely strong.

Currently, most researchers associate the category of intensity with the qualitative-quantitative semantic category. In the work of E. Sheigal, we come across the definition of intensity as a category "located at the intersection of qualitative (indeterminate, non-discrete) and quantitative (level, quantitative) categories." I. I. Turansky also implements a functional-semantic approach to language learning and comes to the same conclusions.

When studying the intensity category, not only well-described intensifiers in modern Russian are of interest, but also intensifiers in which the intensity schema is implicit. This includes parts of speech that form a synonymous series:

rainstorm - heavy rain, whirlwind - strong wind, cry - passionate appeal, squall - very strong wind, triumph - great success, to hate - not to love strongly, to rejoice - to rejoice very much priceless - very expensive, inhuman - very cruel, delightful - very good, disgusting - very unpleasant ugly - very ugly, thunderous - very loud.

In the category of intensity, phraseology and phraseology are among the bright means of expression that enhance the meaning. Occupying an intermediate position between lexical and syntactic means, they give the language an emotional color. It is known that, in addition to strengthening, such tools also improve feelings and values (to distant lands, pour like a bucket, at the top of your lungs, the soul has gone to the heels, etc.).

According to many researchers, stable comparison occupies the most important place among phraseological units and shows one or another feature, which is mainly associated with stereotypes of national culture (Ogol'tsov 1978 ; Lebedeva 1999) (afraid like fire, needed like air, poor like a church rat, dumb like a fish, sweet like honey). It should be noted that these units often enter synomic relations (see: very tired - tired to the point of exhaustion, very quiet - holding your breath, very strong - strong as a diamond). Phraseologisms also contain pure intensifiers that have lost the real comparison feature: hungry like a wolf, like a beast; quirky as it is; you crawl like a turtle; mute like a fish. Comparisons are also noticeable in other units: thin as a skeleton, thin as a worm.

In modern English, the morphological means of intensity are irregular, because they are characteristic only for a part of the lexical units. In the dictionary of linguistic terms edited by Akhmanova, "the degree of superiority of the quality can be considered a morphological tool that expresses the strengthening of the larger dimension of the sign - regardless of the name of the relative" [Akhmanova 1969, 524]: the finest shades, the most beautiful pattern. It is this tool that makes it possible to systematically express the "pure" modification of a feature, not complicated by any additional meaning, and at the same time to convey a subjective, evaluative, expressive meaning. Thus, the relative form (implicit

comparison) is often given to an adjective that includes amplification in its meaning: the greatest dramatic work, the most difficult task, the near future. This phenomenon creates a double amplification effect and is especially common in journalistic text: the wildest rumours; one of the most dense slander; the most universal modern dictator [Rodionova 2005, 164].

In conclusion, the category of intensity has a universal character: the expression of quantity, the parameters of actions, objects and signs, it is actively manifested in different languages. Intensity is directly related to expressiveness. It not only shows the expressiveness of the sentence, but also determines the level of expression. Comparative analysis of intensifiers of all language levels is important in intercultural communication.

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